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ОЦЕНКА МЕДИКАМЕНТОЗНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ СЕРДЦА ПОСЛЕ КОРОНАРНОГО ШУНТИРОВАНИЯ И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПРОГНОЗ В ДОЛГОСРОЧНОЙ ПЕРСПЕКТИВЕ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В исследование включено 354 пациента с сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями, из них 290 мужчин (81,9%) и 64 женщины в возрасте от 36 до 69 лет (18,1%). Средний возраст составил 57,7-7,8 года, 331 из этих пациентов были прооперированы в период с января по декабрь 2020 года. Для сравнения были отобраны 23 пациента с инфарктом миокарда (МИ), которым по тем или иным причинам было назначено консервативное лечение без операции коронарного шунтирования. Изначально, в зависимости от тяжести заболевания и особенностей его течения, использовались консервативные методы лечения сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний. Кардиохирургическое вмешательство позволило улучшить качество жизни некоторых пациентов.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, шунтирование коронарных артерий, ишемическая болезнь сердца.

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EVALUATION OF DRUG TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AFTER CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING AND ITS EFFECT ON LONG-TERM PROGNOSIS

ANNOTATION

The study included 354 patients with CVD—290 men (81.9%) and 64 women aged 36 to 69 years (18.1%). The mean age ranged from 57.7 to 7.8 years, and 331 of these patients underwent surgery between January and December 2020. Twenty-three patients with myocardial infarction (MI) who were treated conservatively without coronary artery bypass surgery for one reason or another were selected for comparison. Initially, conservative methods of cardiovascular treatment were used, depending on the severity of the disease and the peculiarities of its course. Cardiosurgical intervention allows us to improve the quality of life of some patients.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, coronary artery bypass grafting, coronary heart disease

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YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIGI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA AKSH DAN KEYIN MEDIKAMENTOZ DAVOLASHNI BAHOLASH VA UNING UZOQ MUDDATLI PROGNOZGA TA'SIRI

Tadqiqot yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bilan og'rigan 354 bemorni o'z ichiga oladi, ulardan 290 nafari erkaklar (81,9%) va 64 nafari 36 yoshdan 69 yoshgacha (18,1%). O'rtacha yoshi 57,7 - 7,8 yoshni tashkil etdi, ushbu bemorlarning 331 nafari 2020 yil yanvar va dekabr oylari orasida operatsiya qilindi. Taqqoslash uchun, miokard infarkti (mi) bo'lgan 23 bemor tanlangan, ular biron sababga ko'ra jarrohlik revaskulyarizatsiya qilinmagan va konservativ davolangan. Dastlab, kasallikning og'irligiga va uning kursining xususiyatlariga qarab, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarini davolashning konservativ usullari qo'llanilgan. Kardiojarrohlik aralashuvi ba'zi bemorlarning hayot sifatini yaxshilashga imkon berdi.

Kalit so'zlar: yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, aorta koronar shuntlash, yurak ishemik kasalligi

Research shows that exercise that makes one's body work harder can improve one's heart and body in numerous ways. Physical activity improves tissue oxidation-reduction processes, increases steroid hormone levels and normalizes lipid metabolism. Exercise improves myocardial contractile function, stabilizes intracardiac hemodynamics, reduces total peripheral vascular resistance and blood pressure, and reduces myocardial oxygen demand. Regular physical activity reduces the rate of development of stenosing atherosclerosis. After exercise, symptoms of myocardial ischaemia, such as angina pectoris, are reduced or even completely disappear. Exercise can improve physical efficiency, increase self-confidence, boost self-esteem, and improve mood [2; 8].

Rehabilitation practice for each patient requires special care with constant monitoring of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems of patients with myocardial infarction. During the rehabilitation of patients with severe coronary heart disease after aortocoronary bypass in the inpatient stage, these patients are divided into certain groups according to the course of the disease. This load improves coronary blood circulation, improves myocardial contractile and pumping function and improves adaptation mechanisms in the organism. Training exercises should be completely safe for the people performing them, and they should help them improve their physical condition, taking into account their particular health status. Factors such as the type of movement, frequency, intensity and total amount of exercise affect the effectiveness of exercise. Currently, the most common methods for determining the amount of exercise needed are based on the degree of chest pain, the severity of the patient's medical condition, and the degree of physical activity. This advice is mainly designed for group exercise. In this case, the individual approach is slightly neutralized [3; 4; 6].

In patients who have undergone aortocoronary bypass surgery and who are undergoing inpatient rehabilitation, excessive stress may negatively affect their further life activity, which in turn is a factor that seriously undermines the quality of medical services. Therefore, it is very important for doctors to take into account information about patients' physical skills when performing various general strengthening exercises. The age of the patient, the severity of the disease, and the functional state of the musculoskeletal system influence the choice of methods of rehabilitation exercise.

The methods of medical examination used to assess the clinical state of the patient's cardiovascular system should meet the following requirements: to provide information about the increase in the patient's daily routine of various physical exercises and to show the dynamics of the disease; to assess the state of coronary vessels and physical activity; and to assess the level of functional insufficiency of the cardiovascular system [1; 5; 7].

A comparison of conservative and surgical methods for treating diseases of the cardiovascular system is currently common. Assessment of the functional state of the cardiovascular system after aortocoronary bypass surgery (clinical observation, monitoring of heart rhythm, blood pressure and electrocardiogram, biochemical method of blood examination) provides objective information about the general condition of patients. With the help of complex methods, it is possible to fully determine the functional state of the patient and its changes, as well as the degree of functional circulatory weakness (load ECG test, spiroergometry, rheographic study of hemodynamics).

Materials and methods used in the study.

The study included 354 patients aged 36 to 69 years with CVD; 290 of these patients were male (81.9%), and 64 were female (18.1%). From January to December 2020, 331 patients, whose mean age ranged from 57.7 to 7.8 years, underwent elective bypass coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). For comparison, 23 patients with myocardial

infarction (MI) who received conservative treatment and who did not undergo surgical revascularisation for various reasons were studied.

Dynamic examination was carried out during the rehabilitation phase:

- At the hospital stage: From 2018 to 2020, 354 patients were admitted to the cardiology departments of the rehabilitation centre;
- 125 patients were rehabilitated at the sanatorium stage, 95 of whom were at the late hospital stage;
- 86 patients were at the outpatient hospitalization stage.

The majority of patients (291 patients, or 82.2%) suffered from angina pectoris III and IV FC by the time of surgery. A total of 36.2% of patients (128 people) received regular medical care. The average frequency of visits to a cardiologist was 4.1 plus or minus 1.7 (from 1 to 8). Preparation of necessary documents and preoperative examination were the main goals of the majority (55.1%) of all referrals to a doctor, which occurred 3-6 months before hospitalization in the hospital.

In 245 patients (69.2%), total cholesterol levels were determined at least once after CHD onset before surgery (including during the preoperative examination period).

The total CHOL concentration was less than 4.5 mmol/L in 58 (16.4%) patients; in 62 (17.5%) patients, it was between 4.5 and 5.2 mmol/L; in 126 (35.6%) patients, it was between 5.2 and 6.5 mmol/L; and in 108 (30.5%) patients, it exceeded 6.5 mmol/L.

LDL levels were above 3.0 mmol/l in 53.7% (190 patients) and 64.7% (229 patients) of the patients. LDL levels were above 4 mmol/l in 28.5% (101 patients) and above 5 mmol/l in 13.0% (46 patients). A hypertriglyceridaemia level above 1.7 mmol/l was recorded in 44.9% of the patients (159 patients).

Results and discussion

After CABG, drug therapy is extremely important. Much attention has been given to antithrombotic therapy (to prevent thrombus formation in shunts), hypolipidemic therapy (to reduce cholesterol levels and the risk of atherosclerotic plaques) and therapy aimed at preventing heart failure and heart rhythm disorders and maintaining optimal blood pressure.

One of the most important drugs prescribed to patients after CABG surgery is aspirin. It reduces the risk of cardiovascular complications, including myocardial infarction, and significantly improves shunt patency, especially in the first year after surgery. The recommended daily dose of the drug is 100 mg, and it should be taken over a long period of time without interruption or the need for a doctor's prescription.

Statins are the main treatment for lowering blood cholesterol levels. Due to their anti-inflammatory effect, they are recommended for all patients after CABG, even if their blood lipid levels are normal. Statins protect against postoperative rhythm disturbances, particularly by reducing the risk of atrial fibrillation, neurological symptoms and kidney problems. In patients discharged from the hospital after heart repair surgery for CABG, treatment with statins is associated with a lower risk of overall mortality and major cardiac events.

Regardless of the low-density lipoprotein lipid level when treated with statins, all patients undergoing CABG should receive high-intensity statin therapy. Statin therapy should ensure that lipid levels are reduced by 50% or more at baseline from 1.8 to 3.5 mmol/L.

Beta-adrenoblockers are among the most important drugs for the secondary prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients who have undergone angiospastic cardiosclerosis (CABG). They are particularly useful for people with symptoms of heart failure and after myocardial infarction. Carvedilol, bisoprolol and metoprolol are the most common drugs prescribed for this group of patients. Blood pressure, heart rate and other parameters were used to determine the dosage of the drug. To avoid complications such as tachycardia, heart

rhythm disturbances and increased blood pressure, beta-adrenoblockers should be used for a long time and not discontinued on their own.

Patients with cardiovascular pathology are prescribed angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors and anti-otensin II receptor blockers (ARBs) to prevent the development of complications, including heart failure. These agents are most effective in people with hypertension, diabetes, chronic kidney disease, or myocardial infarction and in people with reduced myocardial contractility. The doctor can change the dosage for each patient by monitoring blood pressure.

Diuretics, blood pressure-lowering drugs (e.g., calcium antagonists such as diltiazem or amlodipine), antiarrhythmic drugs and anticoagulants that reduce blood clotting may be prescribed when indicated.

Forty-four (5.3%) patients were not taking antianginal drugs (AADs) for prophylaxis before CABG. A total of 259 patients (31.1%) were receiving AAD, but treatment was episodic or clearly inadequate.

Table 1 shows the evaluation of drug therapy in patients with CHD after CABG during the one-year follow-up.

Five hundred thirty-eight patients (64.1%) received regular AP for at least three months before surgery. AADs were prescribed for 751 patients (90.2%), nitrates for 650 patients (78.0%), ACs for 334 patients (40.1%), preductals for 242 patients (29.1%) and molsidomine for 26 patients (3.1%). Nitrates were taken regularly, and BBs were administered to 63.0% (525/833), 64.1% (534/833) and 15.0% (125/833) of the patients. The remaining patients received treatment infrequently.

A total of 810 (97.2%) patients were taking ASA regularly, 334 (40.1%) were taking ACE inhibitors, 685 (82.2%) were taking lipid-lowering drugs, 342 (41.1%) were taking thiazide diuretics, and 351 (42.1%) were taking medications for comorbidities for at least three months before surgery.

The average dose of AAD is 1.6 per 1 person per day, and the average dose of all drugs is 5.2 per 1 person per day.

Table 1

Drug therapy for patients with CHD after CABG

Medicines	CHD patients after non-CABG (n=833)					
	before CABG		After 6 months.		After 12 months.	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
DAPT : - Ticagrelor 180 mg/day • Clopidogrel 75 mg/day	433	52,0	433	52,0	299	35,9
Aspirin 100 mg/day	334	40,1	775	93,0	665	79,8
Beta-blockers	751	90,2	758	91,0	633	76,0
ACE inhibitors	700	84,0	620	74,4	550	66,0
Angiotensin receptor antagonists	100	12,0	263	31,6	180	21,6
Diuretics	400	48,0	279	33,5	143	17,2
Nitrates	650	78,0	309	37,1	123	14,8
Calcium antagonists	334	40,1	133	16,0	94	11,3
Statins	685	82,2	833	100	720	86,4
Warfarin	133	16,0	68	8,2	0	0
DOAC (rivaroxaban, dabigatran)	133	16,0	0	0	0	0

Note. DAPT- dual antiplatelet therapy; ACE inhibitors-angiotensin converting enzymes; DOAC- oral anticoagulants.

The mandatory therapy for patients undergoing CABG is as follows:

1) Plavix - 75 mg daily 5 days before stenting, then for 3-4 months for both groups of patients, thrombo-ASS (or aspirin-cardio) - 100 mg daily at bedtime continuously;

2) Norvasc (5 mg) or altiazem (diltiazem) (180 mg) once a day 7-10 days before the intervention and 5-6 months after the intervention;

3) According to individual indications, the following were used: betalok-ZOC, 50-100 mg once a day; concor, 5 mg once a day (continuously); prestarium, 2-4 mg; monopril, 5-10 mg; dirotone, 5-10 mg once a day; or quinapril, 5-10 mg daily.

4) Atorvastatin (Liprimar) - 10 mg once daily at any time or simvastatin (Zocor) - 20 mg once daily at bedtime 2-3 weeks before the intervention and 5-6 months after the intervention.

The mortality rate during dynamic follow-up was 3.8% at 12 months (32 out of 833 patients). We were interested in the identification of factors. Influencing cardiovascular mortality of patients after CABG

The analysis showed that the use of beta-adrenoblockers, low-density lipoprotein levels, the atherogenicity index, left ventricular ejection function, duration of surgery, occurrence of major risk and occurrence of acute renal failure in the postoperative period strongly influenced patients' quality of life (Table 2).

Multiple logistic regression revealed only three independent factors determining the occurrence of this adverse outcome: preoperative atherogenicity index (hazard ratio (HR)) 1.40 and 95% confidence interval (CI) 1.06-1.85; p=0.02), reduced left ventricular ejection fraction (HR=0.96; 95% CI=0.91-0.99; p=0.04) and the development of acute renal failure after surgery (HR=5.59; 95% CI=1.40-22.34; p=0.01).

The results of scientific analyses have shown that fatal outcomes occurring within 1 year after surgery may be due to additional effects on coronary vessels (such as the timely administration of drugs, low-density lipoprotein levels, patient age or comorbidities). etc.) (Table 3).

Table 2

Factors influencing cardiovascular mortality in patients undergoing CABG

Factor	OR (95% CI)	P
Single-factor analysis		
Taking β-adrenoblockers	0.14 (0.04-0.47)	0.01
Taking statins	0.36 (0.14-1.06)	0.06

Low-density lipoproteins	1.29 (1.00-1.69)	0.01
Index of atherogenicity	1.26 (1.00-1.58)	0.06
End-diastolic size of the left ventricle	1.85 (1.09-3.10)	0.03
Left ventricular ejection fraction	0.96 (0.93-0.99)	0.03
Thickness of the intima-media complex	1.48 (0.95-232.16)	0.07
Multivariate analysis		
Index of atherogenicity	1.40(1.06-1.85)	0.02
Left ventricular ejection fraction	0.96(0.91-0.99)	0.04
Acute renal failure in the hospital period	5.59(1.40-22.34)	0.01

Note: OR—odds ratio; CI—confidence interval

Table 3

Factor	OR(95% CI)	P
Single-factor analysis		
Taking β -adrenoblockers	0.23 (0.07-0.73)	0.01
Atherogenicity index	1.34(1.02-1.75)	0.032
End-diastolic size of the left ventricle	1.87(1.09-3.20)	0.023
Left ventricular ejection fraction	0.96 (0.92-0.99)	0.027
Thickness of the intima-media complex	10.39 (0.74-146.49)	0.083
Number of coronary arteries affected	1.90(1.08-3.34)	0.027
Multivariate analysis		
Duration of artificial circulation	1.01 (1.00-1.03)	0.009
Postinfarction cardiosclerosis	3.16(1.02-9.79)	0.046

The results of a comprehensive analysis showed that the one-year prognosis after aortocoronary bypass surgery has a negative impact on the quality of life of patients with independent MI and postinfarction cardiosclerosis due to lesions in other vessels.

Thus, the overall mortality of patients was 3.8% during the year after coronary artery bypass surgery. Factors associated with coronary death during the year were inadequate use of beta-blockers, low-density lipoprotein serum levels, an atherogenic index, decreased left ventricular pumping function, duration of surgery, and initial risk. The postoperative atherogenic index and reduced left ventricular ejection fraction influenced the specific outcome according to multiple logistic regression analysis.

Conclusion.

We found that 44 (5.3%) patients with CHD were not taking antianginal drugs (AADs) prior to drug therapy administered after coronary artery bypass grafting, and this did not affect the long-term prognosis. A total of 259 patients (31.1%) were receiving AP, but treatment was episodic or clearly inadequate. Five hundred thirty-eight

patients (64.1%) received regular AADs for at least three months before surgery. AADs were prescribed for 751 patients (90.2%), nitrates for 650 patients (78.0%), ACs for 334 patients (40.1%), preductal for 242 patients (29.1%) and molsidomine for 26 patients (3.1%). Nitrates were taken regularly, and BBs were administered to 63.0% (525/833), 64.1% (534/833) and 15.0% (125/833) of the patients. The remaining patients received treatment infrequently.

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The results of the analysis revealed the use of β -blockers, low-density lipoprotein levels, the atherogenicity index, the left ventricular ejection fraction, the duration of surgery, the baseline risk and the risk of acute renal failure in the postoperative period. Moreover, surgery increases the risk of cardiovascular mortality within one year after surgery.

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